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Writing feedback and production mediated by technologies: possibilities and challenges

Revista Letras Raras (RLR), a scholarly journal of Linguistics and Literature, from the Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity (Federal University of Campina Grande), launches the edition number 2, from volume 10, on this May of 2021 – a year particularly made of high hopes. Especially in this edition, the challenges of researchers and other professionals in the area of Letters are the key to our reflections.

This issue has the collaboration of scholars-researchers from universities at different regions of Brazil: Roberta Varginha Ramos Caiado, from the Catholic University of Pernambuco (UNICAP); Adair Vieira Gonçalves, from the Federal University of Grande Dourados (UFGD) and a researcher at the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (UFGD/CNPq); Eliana Maria Severino Donoio Ruiz, from the State University of Londrina (UEL); and Milene Bazarim, from the Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG) and the Catholic University of Pernambuco (UNICAP). These researchers, altogether, conducted the issue **Writing feedback and production mediated by technologies: possibilities and challenges**, in which the reader will find papers, an essay, a review, an interview, and creative literary texts from equally diverse origins.

In this second edition there are researchers who contribute mainly to the domain of the issue, but also with reflections founded in the field of Applied Linguistics, Discourse Analysis, and Literature for young people and children. The authors of the papers and texts of artistic or literary creation come from different places: Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC), Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), Federal University of Pernambuco (UFPE), Federal University of Campina Grande, Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais (CEFET/Leopoldina campus/MG), Catholic University of Pernambuco, State University of Paraíba (UEPB), Federal University of Grande Dourados, Federal University of Ouro Preto (UFOP), Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG), Federal University of Latin American Integration (UNILA/Foz do Iguaçu), Colégio Pedro II (Rio de Janeiro), Fluminense Federal University (UFF), *Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas* (Conicet), *Instituto de Investigaciones en Humanidades y*

Ciencias Sociales (IdiHCS) from the National University of La Plata (Argentina), University of Évora (Portugal), and *Università degli Studi di Perugia* (Italy). For the creative texts, there are authors who come from the University of Passo Fundo (UPF), the Federal Institute of Rio Grande do Sul (IFRS/Passo Fundo), the Federal University of Espírito Santo (UFES), as well as from public schools in the cities of Campos dos Goytacazes (PMCG/SEDUCT/EMJP) and Duque de Caxias (PMDC/SMEDC/EMJF).

Dear reader, in this second edition for our journal's tenth year, you will be able to turn on your mobile camera to the journal's QR Code and to the text you want to read. You can also share the text with your colleagues and/or students. Thus, we will resist not only the adverse context surrounding us, but also survive by the act of resistance.

Shall we keep on going through the sanitary health crisis in social distancing, but close to each other by knowledge production. In order to contribute with it, dear reader, we wish you a great reading!

Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz

Marco Antônio Margarido Costa

Maria Angélica de Oliveira

Editors of *Revista Letras Raras*: A Scholarly Journal of the Research Group LELLC – Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity / Federal University of Campina Grande.

Translated by Rafael de Arruda Sobral.